

Identifying wrinkle ridges structures from Mars MGS and Viking mission data: using Grass in planetary geology.

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Abstract

The numerous missions to Mars have sent information about the red planet during last decades. Recently it has been shown that Mars has ice on its poles and that ice could be probably present all over the planet subsurface. The presence of ice on subsurface could drive particular geological structures. The so called 'wrinkle ridges' structures could be related to this. Grass GIS has been used to import and store in a common geospatial database Viking image data and the latest Mars Global Surveyor (MGS) data. GRASS raster based analysis at different resolution has been used to identify wrinkle structures. The image modules are used to align Viking data with Mars Orbiter Laser Altimeter (MOLA) DEM.

1 Introduction

The large quantity of data coming from missions to Mars made necessary to deal with an efficient system of storage/retrieval of these data. Planetary Data System (PDS) represents a good example of distributed archiving system. The analysis of the data is thereafter difficult due to different reference systems and data heterogeneity. In this work GRASS GIS has been used to import and analyse dataset from MGS and Viking PDS archives.

The case study is the morpho-geological analysis of wrinkle ridges structures present in different zones of the planet. Along with the working activity, the possible use of GRASS with planetary data has been studied, underlying the extra feature needed to embed in GRASS GIS to use it as efficient analysis tool for planetary data.

2 Mars Data: a common format

When data coming from scientific missions tend to be large in quantity, the risk of losing them increases. But in this case another risk is present: a particular dataset could be almost impossible to access [11].

Bill Quade, Chief of the Science Branch of the Solar System Exploration Division, NASA Headquarters, took the steps necessary to establish a system to preserve planetary data and provide access to them [11]. In the early 1980s Bill Quade established the Planetary Science Data Steering Group (PSDSG) that convened a Planetary Data Workshop in 1983 to put the basis of the Planetary Data System.

The NASA Planetary Data System (PDS) is an archive that provides high quality, usable planetary science data products to the science community. The PDS is a distributed system composed of eight nodes [8]. Five of these nodes represent specific science subjects, these are: Atmospheres, Geosciences, Planetary Plasma Interactions, Rings, Small Bodies. The remaining three nodes are the support nodes: the Imaging Node, the JPL Navigation Ancillary Information (NAIF) and the Central Node (situated at the Jet Propulsion Laboratory).

Since PDS stores heterogeneous data (from instruments reading to documentation) and the access to data has to be easily affordable, an Object Description Language (ODL) is used to describe document contents. ODL is a sort of simple language made by the

Figure 1: Planetocentric system

pair keyword/value. The most important feature of ODL is that it is both human and machine readable. Usually ODL is included as ASCII strings at the start of a PDS document. All the information of the dataset is reported including the byte offset where the data will start (in the case of binary data). PDS data is available for download directly from the 'nodes', or by request CDROMs directly to Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL). Several institutions are making web based search engines for retrieving PDS data in an interactive way [3]. PDS is well documented [5] and there are several software tools in binary and source form to help access the data.

3 Mars reference systems

The relatively young research activity on Mars led the need of the institution of NASA's Mars Geodesy/Cartography Working Group (MGCWG) in 1998 to avoid repeating the experience of 1970s-80s when competing researchers produced maps of Mars mutually inconsistent, choosing different geodetic control solutions [2]. MGCWG has then assembled a set of preferred values for Mars cartographic constants based on best available data. These values are then transmitted to the International Astronomical Union (IAU) that publishes them on specific reports [14].

Prime Meridian The location of prime meridian is defined by the centre of crater Airy-0. The exact positioning of this point is very important, as any change will result in a change of longitude definition of every Mars' geographic feature. During Viking Orbiter and Mariner 9, the position of Airy-0 has been determined photogrammetrically. MGS Mars Orbital Laser Altimeter (MOLA) observations allow an order of accuracy of 100m in horizontal position.

Reference Surface Although actual data show that Mars' shape could be approximated by a triaxial ellipsoid, the uncertainties of measurements allow to approximate it to a sphere with radius of $r = 3389.50 \pm 0.2km$ or a rotational ellipsoid with equatorial axis $a = 3396.19 \pm 0.1km$ and a polar radius of $b = 3376.20 \pm 0.1km$ (IAU2000) [14]. The best fitting rotational ellipsoid gives a root-mean-square (RMS) deviation from spheroid of 3.0km.

Coordinate System IAU in 1970 formalised the use of two coordinate systems for planets:

East/Planetocentric: longitude measured positive eastward and latitude defined as the angle between the equatorial plane and a line from the centre of the body to a given point (figure 1). Planetocentric is called aerocentric for Mars.

West/Planetographic: longitude measured positive westward and latitude defined as the angle between the equatorial plane and the normal to a spheroidal reference surface at a given point (figure 2). Planetographic is called aerographic for Mars.

Because of the flatness of Mars, planetographic latitude at any point is greater than the corresponding planetocentric latitude; the maximum difference between the two types of latitude is about 0.3 degree (about 20 km) at 45 degrees north and south [6]. All USGS data products since 1970s have used the West/Planetographic system, while from MGS the East/Planetocentric system has been adopted, therefore dealing with these data means to take into account both the coordinate systems.

Figure 2: Planetographic system

Figure 3: The system adopted in Grass

4 Choose of a reference system for Mars data in GRASS

Since, at the moment, GRASS doesn't have specific approved IAU coordinate system we must choose a system that permits to utilise Mars data. In figures 1 and 2 the two IAU systems are shown while the system chosen to analyse data in GRASS is reported in figure 3 .

5 Importing PDS data into GRASS

From all available PDS data, we import into Grass: Viking Mars Digital Image Mosaic (MDIM), MGS MOLA Mission Experiment Gridded Data Record (MEGDR) and MGS Mars Orbiter Camera (MOC). The Viking MDIM are greyscale images with resolution of 255 pixel per degree. The MEGDR is a DEM with a resolution of 1/64 degree per pixel (about 930 meters). The MOC data pushes resolution from 230–500 meters per pixel of wide angle (WA) shots to 5–1 meters per pixel for narrow angle (NA) images [4].

Viking and MGS image data (respectively MDIM2.0/2.1 and MOC) are stored in an image (x,y) GRASS LOCATION. Importing data into GRASS from PDS non compressed format is straightforward since all information on byte offset and data structure are described in the ASCII header. Using the GNU utility `dd` is then possible to get the binary part to be imported with `r.in.bin`.

An alternative way to import PDS image data is through the GNU Image Manipulation Program (*GIMP*¹) together with a PDS plug-in written by Holger Isenberg² and then import it with `r.in.*` image importing modules. MOLA MEGDR is directly imported in a Lat/Lon LOCATION through `r.in.bin`.

The images are then grouped and referenced using `i.*` modules. Since coordinates of the vertex of the images are reported in PDS header, suitable-for-text-processing *GNU-AWK*, *Perl*, *Python* could be used for writing a `$LOCATION/$MAPSET/group/POINTS` file to be read by `i.rectify`. We opted for a simple *Python* script in order to extract PDS

¹<http://www.gimp.org>

²Source code is available at <http://mars-news.de/gimp/>

Figure 4: `ps.map` output of Solis Planum region data stored in Grass

header data, to convert latitude and longitude to local GRASS reference system and to write a `POINTS` file.

MDIM2.0 is in planetographic coordinates, based on IAU1991 ellipsoid ($a=3396.0$ km, $b=3376.8$ km) and MGS MOLA MEGDR DEM is distributed using a planetocentric system based on a sphere (an aeroid surface with a radius of 3396.0 Km). In the case of a sphere, planetographic and planetocentric latitudes coincide.

The geometries of Mars spheroids have been included in `etc/ellipse.table` and `etc/datum.table`.

6 A case study: Wrinkle Ridges

Wrinkle ridges are linear to sub-linear positive land-forms and represent horizontal shortening in planetary lithosphere. They are common on several planetary bodies, including Mars, Earth, Venus, the Moon and Mercury. On Mars they are typically found on ridged plains, that are extensive flows of basaltic lava [13].

Applying on Mars the basic concept of structural geology commonly applied on the Earth, most models agree that wrinkle ridges are related to antiformal structures linked to some deep detachment [10, 12]. Basically the wrinkle ridges are considered as detachment folds formed as the result of shortening and displacement of a layer of strong rock above a weak layer.

Detachment zones on Mars could be found in relation of shallow subsurface ice in certain zones on the planet, whose existence has been recently confirmed [1].

In this scenario, the iced levels on Mars represent the weak layers on which the above harder rocks (basaltic rocks of the ridges plains) can move giving origin to the wrinkle ridges.

Solis Planum region presents impressive wrinkle ridges and is one of the few regions

Figure 5: Topographic profile along the trace shown in figure 4. Vertical scale is exaggerated to show the steps-like trend

where MOC NA camera registered high resolution imagery data of a wrinkle ridge. Although this region has already been inspected [9, 7], raw, non processed PDS data is imported and analysed in Grass.

In figure 4 a shot of region Solis Planum is presented. The base raster is the MEGDR DEM, while the image in the centre is a Viking MDIM. The height ranges from 1145 (green) to 4151 (red) meters.

The two rasters are overlaid by contours with an equidistance of 250 meters built from MEGDR DEM. The location of MOC WA image is indicated by the squared grey frame inside the Viking image area.

The region presents sub parallel wrinkle ridges structures spaced of about 90 km in the North-Western sector and 70 km in the central portion of the image.

In figure 4 is also reported the trace of a topographic profile along the region. The profile (figure 5) shows clearly a steps-like trend with a difference of altitude of about 125 meters between each plain.

In figure 6 a close-up of a two wrinkle ridges is shown, together with MOC WA image M0203135. Vertical range is from 1966 (green) to 3004 meters (red). The topographic profile (figure 7) shows the asymmetry of the structures. In the slope map (not shown, generated with `r.slope.aspect` module) we read that the NW limb slope is from 2 to 4 degrees while at SE the slope is about 6 degrees. Shape and asymmetry of the structures are similar.

The MOC NA image (figure 8) shows at great detail the morphology of a wrinkle ridge. The trace of C-D profile is reported.

7 Conclusions

Analysis of planetary data using Grass is then possible. Grass has a huge number of modules for geographic data analysis, and these can be very useful for an in-depth analysis of non-terrestrial celestial bodies.

The availability of large, well documented dataset, together with the free availability of source code, would make Grass a good tool for planetary research.

The primary need to make so is to implement the IAU recommended reference systems so to maintain data interchange possible and to avoid confusion. Then specific modules could help in importing planetary data.

Figure 6: Subregion of map shown in figure 4

Figure 7: Topographic profile along the trace shown in figure 6. Vertical scale is exaggerated to show the wrinkle's shape.

Figure 8: Detail of the M0203134 MOC Narrow Angle image with the trace of topographic profile CD (figure 7).

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